

DEVIATIONS OF MEROCYANINES DERIVED FROM BENZOTHIAZOLE AND SUBSTITUTED RHODANINES

BY B. K. SABATA, B. K. PATNAIK AND M. K. ROUT

Vinylogous merocyanines ($n=0, 1, 2$ and 3), derived from substituted rhodanines and benzothiazole, have been described. Absorption maxima of the compounds have been measured and the deviations calculated after taking into account the relative data for the corresponding symmetrical cyanines and oxonols. Effect of increasing chain length (by addition of vinyl groups) on the deviation in the above merocyanines has also been determined.

In view of the observations already reported (Brooker *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5326) that deviation is greatly influenced by the extent of basicity or of acidity of the constituent nuclei in merocyanines, the effect of varying substitution on the rhodanine nucleus and that of increase in chain length on the deviations of merocyanines, derived from benzothiazole and rhodanines, have been studied.

Mero-, merocarbo-, merodicarbo-, and merotricarbo-cyanines (I) derived from substituted rhodanines as the acidic component, and benzothiazole as the basic component have been prepared for this investigation.

The absorption data of the above merocyanines (in pyridine) are recorded in Tables I—IV.

The deviations of the individual merocyanines were calculated by taking into consideration the absorption maximum of the merocyanine concerned and of the corresponding symmetrical cyanine and the oxonol. The procedure is illustrated below by taking the case of merocarbo-cyanine ($I: n=1$), corresponding symmetrical cyanine and oxonol of which are (II) and (III) respectively.

The compound (II : $n=1$) and the oxonol (III : $n=0$) absorb at 565 and 522 $m\mu$. If the two extreme structures of the merocyanine (I : $n=1$) were of the same energy, it would have absorbed at 543.5 $m\mu$, the mean value of the absorption maxima for (II : $n=1$) and (III : $n=0$). But actually its absorption maximum lies at 510 $m\mu$, i.e., it falls short of the mean value by 33.5 $m\mu$, which is therefore the deviation in this case.

The deviations for the mero-dicarbocyanines and mero-tricarbocyanines were similarly calculated by considering respectively the absorption maxima values of (a) (I : $n=2$), (II : $n=2$), (III : $n=1$) for the mero-dicarbocyanine and (b) (I : $n=3$), (II : $n=3$), (III : $n=2$) for the mero-tricarbocyanine and were found to be 40 $m\mu$ and 102 $m\mu$. The absorption maxima for the mono-, tri-, and penta-methinoxonols are considered to be 522, 620 and 715 $m\mu$ respectively, and those for the tri-, penta- and hepta- methincyanines, 565, 660 and 760 $m\mu$ respectively.

The above discussion indicates that deviation increases with increase in chain length.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methylmercaptobenzothiazole Metho-p-toluenesulphonate.—2-Methylmercaptobenzothiazole (3.62 g.) and methyl *p*-toluenesulphonate (3.72 g.) were heated for 16 hours at 110°. The solid cake obtained was pulverised, washed with acetone, and dried, m.p. 162°. It was directly used for dye formation without further purification.

5-(3-Methylbenzothiazolin-2-ylidene)-3-phenylrhodanine.—The preceding sulphonate (6.32 g.) and phenylrhodanine (0.2 g.) were refluxed in absolute ethanol in presence of triethylamine for 7 minutes. The compound separated in straw-yellow plates. It was filtered hot and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. > 280°, yield 70%. (Found : C, 56.40 ; H, 3.27. $C_{17}H_{12}ON_2S_2$ requires C, 56.53 ; H, 3.37%). The other merocyanines of this series are described in Table I.

TABLE I

R.	<i>Merocyanines (I: n=0).</i>						
	M.P.	Yield	λ_{max}	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Phenyl	280°	70%	430 $m\mu$	56.40	56.53	3.27	3.37
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	265°	40	430	58.20	58.39	3.62	3.78
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	280°	68	430	58.30	58.39	3.67	3.78
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	280°	75	430	58.28	58.39	3.70	3.78
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	280°	65	430	52.08	52.24	3.42	3.54

5-Ethoxymethylene-3-phenylrhodanine.—3-Phenylrhodanine (2.0 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (3 g.) were refluxed in pyridine for 5 minutes. After removing excess of pyridine under reduced pressure, the product was added to water. The crude product after washing with ethanol was used for dye formation without further purification. The pure material was obtained by recrystallisation from ethanol, m.p. 175°, yield 50%. (Found : C, 54.28 ; H, 4.03. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2NS_2$ requires C, 54.35 ; H, 4.15%).

5-[(3-Methyl-2-benzothiazolinylidene)-ethylidene]-3-phenylrhodanine.—The above rhodanine (0.25 g.) and 2-methylbenzothiazole methiodide (0.29 g.) were refluxed in absolute ethanol and

triethylamine for 7 minutes. The product separating on cooling was filtered, dried, and recrystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 168-69°, yield 50%. (Found: C, 59.50; H, 3.60. $C_{18}H_{14}ON_2S_2$ requires C, 59.68; H, 3.66%). The other merocyanines of this series are described in Table II.

TABLE II

Merocarbocyanines (I : n=1).

R.	M.P.	Yield.	$\lambda_{max.}$	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Phenyl	168-69°	50%	510 $m\mu$	59.50	59.68	3.60	3.66
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	164°	35	510	61.12	61.44	3.98	4.04

2-(4-Acetanilido-1 : 3-butadienyl)-benzothiazole Methiodide.—2-Methylbenzothiazole methiodide (2.91 g.) and β -anilinoacrolein anil hydrochloride (2.58 g.) were heated under reflux in acetic anhydride (15-18 c.c.) for 70 minutes. The mixture was cooled and treated with ether, when a gummy mass was obtained. This solidified on being kept in contact with methanol. The product thus obtained was washed with acetone, affording a product pure enough to be used for dye formation. The pure material was obtained by recrystallisation from acetic acid, m.p. 160-62°, yield 40%. (Found: C, 51.31; H, 4.02. $C_{20}H_{19}ON_2IS$ requires C, 51.94; H, 4.11%).

5-[4-(3-Methylbenzothiazolin-2-ylidene)-buten-1-ylidene]-3-phenylrhodanine.—The above intermediate (4.6 g.) and 3-phenylrhodanine (2.0 g.) were boiled in absolute ethanol (20 c.c.) and triethylamine (1 g.) for 3 minutes. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol, and finally recrystallised from hot methanol from which it separated in green needles, m.p. 177°, yield 60%. (Found: C, 61.62; H, 3.78. $C_{21}H_{18}ON_2S_3$ requires C, 61.75; H, 3.92%). The other merocyanines of this series are described in Table III.

TABLE III

Merodicarbocyanines.

R.	M.P.	Yield.	$\lambda_{max.}$	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Phenyl	177°	60%	600 $m\mu$	61.62	61.75	3.78	3.92
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	194°	30	605	61.88	62.17	4.18	4.27
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	168-69°	50	600	62.03	62.17	4.05	4.27
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	188°	42	600	62.13	62.17	3.98	4.27

2-(6-Acetanilido-1 : 3 : 5-hexatrienyl)-benzothiazole Methiodide.—2-Methylbenzothiazole methiodide (2.91 g.) and glutamic aldehyde dianilide hydrochloride (2.84 g.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride for 6 minutes. The reaction mixture was treated with ether, when the solid product separated out. The product after acetone-wash was directly used for dye formation. Pure material was obtained by recrystallisation from acetic acid, m.p. 163° (decomp.), yield 35%. (Found: C, 53.27; H, 4.14. $C_{22}H_{21}ON_2IS$ requires C, 53.99; H, 4.29%).

5-[6-(Methylbenzothiazolin-2-ylidene)-hexa-2 : 4-dien-1-ylidene]-3-phenylrhodanine.—The above intermediate (4.88 g.) and 3-phenylrhodanine (2 g.) were boiled in absolute ethanol and triethylamine (1.0 g.) for 2 minutes. The product separating on chilling was filtered, air-dried, and

recrystallised from hot methanol in green needles, m.p. 180°, yield 60%. (Found: C, 60.58; H, 3.74. $C_{23}H_{19}ON_2S_2$ requires C, 60.79; H, 3.96%). The other merocyanines of this series are described in Table IV.

TABLE IV
Merotricarbocyanines.

R.	M.P.	λ_{max}	Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Phenyl	180°	635 $m\mu$	60%	60.58	60.79	3.74	3.86
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	224°	635	30	63.01	63.21	4.42	4.46
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	188-89°	635	35	63.13	63.21	4.25	4.46
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	170°	635	40	63.08	63.21	4.31	4.46

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MAYURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE, CUTTACK-3,
ORISSA.

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